

A PILOT STUDY ON FINE-TUNING NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION FOR CLINICAL TAG EXTRACTION USING PRETRAINED LANGUAGE MODELS: THE TUT-ALL EXPERIENCE

Adeyemi Victor Gbadamosi¹, Alberto Montero², Martin Deutsch², Nick Sander², Claire Cashmore¹, Eva Sousa^{1,3*}

1: Centre of Excellence for Data Science, Artificial Intelligence and Modelling, University of Hull, Hull, United Kingdom

e-mail: adeyemi.gbadamosi@yahoo.com, {c.cashmore, e.sousa}@hull.ac.uk

web: <https://www.hull.ac.uk/work-with-us/research/institutes/data-science-artificial-intelligence-and-modelling>

2: Tut-All Software GmbH, Munich, Germany

e-mail: {alberto.montero, martin.deutsch, nick.sander}@tut-all.com web: <http://tut-all.com/mytutall.html>

3: Centre for Biomedicine, Hull York Medical School, University of Hull, Hull, United Kingdom

e-mail: eva.sousa@hyms.ac.uk*web: Centre for Biomedicine | Hull York Medical School

Keywords: Named entity extraction, BioElectra, BioLinkBert, PubMedBert, Pretrained language models (PLMs), Tut-All

Abstract *The standard procedure to extract data from medical records is still a laborious process where research analysts examine a wide range of information sources. Hence, there is a strong need to improve automatic data extraction techniques. This study performed fine-tuning of the pretrained language models (PLMs)—BioElectra, PubMedBert, BioLinkBert, and Clinical Longformer—for named entity recognition (NER) in clinical texts. The clinical texts were extracted from records using the Tut-All software and were comprised of abstracts and methods sections. For performance analysis the mean of the F1-score for each named entity tag was used across different hyperparameter optimizations. PubMedBert achieved the best performance results with a mean F1-score of 0.638 and an output range of 0.3. This performance was achieved after training with a learning rate and a weight decay of 5×10^{-5} and 3×10^{-3} respectively, employing default HuggingFace hyperparameters. Notably, PubMedBert exhibited superior performance on minority entity types, addressing a key challenge in real-world data applications. The optimized model not only expedites information retrieval, but also enhances the overall quality of extracted data, marking a valuable contribution to the data extraction data from medical records.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the intersection of healthcare and technology has seen significant breakthroughs, and one of the driving forces behind this change has been the quick development of Natural Language Processing with the use of Pretrained Language Models (PLMs) for Named Entity Recognition (NER) [1].

In the biomedical domain, a fundamental task of Natural Language Processing is the recognition of named entities, such as genes, diseases, species, chemicals, medical codes or drug names [2]. In an era where the volume of medical literature and patient data is growing exponentially the ability of PLMs to extract important entities in an automated way from complex medical texts is essential [3].

The importance of the information in healthcare is in part supported by the growing paradigm of evidence-based medicine, which emerged with the XXI century [4] and is being transformed by the advent of Artificial Intelligence techniques [5]. This new era of evidence-based medicine is not only essential for advancing medical research and exploring the effectiveness of new drugs or side-effects, but mostly to manage the growing amount of data generated [6]. Named Entity Recognition (NER), and PLMs play a crucial role in this process [7].

To create databases used for this supported decision, in clinic or in research, medical researchers synthesize knowledge by combining information from multiple articles information to identify trends, patterns, and inconsistencies [8], [9]. This process is many times done manually but can be greatly streamlined and automatized by applying NER algorithms in the identification and categorization of specific entities within clinical publications [10].

Randomized controlled trials have been for some time the cornerstone of evidence practise medicine, as reliable evidence information for clinical decision [11], [12], [13]. Randomized controlled trials measure the effectiveness of a new intervention or reducing the bias and providing a rigorous tool to examine cause-effect relationships between an intervention and outcomes, due to the randomization of intervention and subjects treated [14]. The possibility to extract and compile the information of multiple registry repositories of randomized controlled trials is hence very attractive as database information used for support to healthcare decisions, development of pharmaceuticals or the creation of policies [15], [16]. By accurately identifying and categorizing key information, NER algorithms can help on revolutionizing clinical trials and ultimately on accelerating health research breakthroughs [17], [18], [19].

This modern era of PLMs began with the introduction of word embedding models, such as Word2Vec [20] and GloVe [21]. These models laid the foundation for algorithms that encode the relationships and contextual meanings of words in a text [20], [21].

Over the years, the field has witnessed significant progress, from the transformer architecture [22] to techniques like Embedding from Language Models (ELMo) [23] and Universal Language Model Fine-Tuning (ULMFiT) [24]. Transformer models have particularly revolutionized natural language processing by demonstrating improved ability to manage dependencies between words in a sentence [25] leading to breakthroughs in NER that align well with Evidence-Based Medicine, with some models already being trained for use in NER of medical entities [25], [26].

Some of these models achieve good results with clinical NER, namely BioElectra [27], PubMedBert [28], [29], [30], BioLinkBert [31], and Clinical Longformer [32], [33]. These models were then chosen as they demonstrated superior metrics compared to other medically fine-tuned pretrained large language models. All of them have been fine-tuned on medical literature to have adaptations specifically tailored for medical applications [28], [29], [30], [32], [33], [34]. It is important to note that Clinical Longformer has the unique advantage of not being constrained by the 512-token limitation observed in the Bert models, which enhances the model's capacity to capture and interpret extensive medical text, expanding the scope and depth of the possible analysis [33].

The aim of this research was to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of entity extraction, recurring to PLMs in the clinical text databases property of the company Tut-All Software GmbH, located in Karlsruhe, Germany. Tut-All Software GmbH does annotation & data extraction of randomized clinical trials, as well as training of people within this field. By fine-tuning these models on a custom data set using Tut-All databases the research aimed to improve the extraction of predefined medical entities, aiding in the automation of evidence-based medicine. Ultimately, this research aimed to contribute to more efficient data retrieval and better-quality controlled in medical research, helping researchers and practitioners make informed decisions.

2. METHODS

2.1 Data sets

In this study 4 data sets were created and used to train the PLMs in the clinical entities' recognition tasks.

For the creation of the training data sets the randomized clinical trials databases property of Tut-All Software GmbH has been used. This database constitutes 1549 randomized controlled trials manually annotated by research analysts, with the help of a Scientific Workflow Tool (SWT) designed by Tut-All Software GmbH as described in figure 1.

The SWT is a tool where data from randomized controlled trials are selected, assessed and extracted manually and automatically.

These variables are values attributed to the entities, which need to be recognised in each publication. A basic workflow of this process can be also seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Workflow of the process, from the paper selection and step done with the SWT to the results using the PLMs.

The initial annotation process of the 1549 clinical records originated 2816 tags. These tags represent various entity types within the SWT, such as:

CONDITION: Category of words that describe clinical condition (e.g. COPD, pneumonia, ...).

DESIGN: Category of words that describe the design of the study (e.g. Randomized controlled trial double blinded, ...).

SUBJECTS: Category of words that describe the subjects of the study (e.g. adults non-smokers, ...).

GROUPS: Category of words that describe the samples of randomization (e.g. group A (medication A), group B (medication B), ...).

Subsequently, the abstracts and methods of each clinical record were collated with their corresponding tags and organized into a JSON file. Further refining the data set involved identifying and tagging entities within the abstracts and methods based on the context, resulting in the creation of two initial data sets. Recognizing the limitations of BERT-based models, which can only handle 512 tokens, the abstract data set underwent additional segmentation, leading to the generation of two additional data sets with varying total text lengths. The final four data sets created contained:

Abstract only – abstract of the record and the entity in the abstract.

Abstract and methods – abstract from the record merged with the methods increasing the total

length of the text.

Abstract and methods: 50 tokens segments – abstract and method were split into chunks of 50 (words and punctuation) by counting the tokens.

Abstract and methods: 512 tokens segments – abstract and method were split into chunks of 512 tokens (words and punctuation) by counting the tokens.

These summarized characteristics of the resultant data sets used are described in table 1.

	Abstract only	Abstract with method	Abstract and methods (50 tokens)	Abstract and methods (512 tokens)
Total data sets	1549	1549	50046	5563
Training samples	1239	1239	40036	4450
Validation samples	155	155	5005	557
Testing samples	155	155	5005	556

Table 1. The base description of the data set after processing the raw data from the SWT in preparation for training and fine-tuning. The abstract with methods data has 5 times more texts and 3 times more unique texts in the data.

2.2. Labels

To create the labelled data set for the training raw JSON files have been used, created from the information extracted of randomized controlled trials with the SWT. These raw JSON files contained 1549 dictionaries with 5 identification keys, described below:

PMID: PubMed reference number for records indexed in PubMed

Title: Title of the record

TEXT: Abstract or method depending on what was extracted by the SWT

CONTEXT: Context of the annotated text containing the surrounding words for a biunique mapping

ANNOTATIONS: Entities and their corresponding entity type.

From these identification keys, the context is the reference for the others to be applied after, as it ensured that only the right entity in the text was matched. In figure 2 it is possible to see this process exemplified.

Figure 2. Overview of the labelling methodology, starting from the empty labels to the labelled output with the correct tags and the final tag representations to be used in training.

As can be seen in figure 2, an empty label with equal length to the full-length text was created first. After that, the index of the context in the text was determined by matching the context in the full-length text. This served as the bounding range for the entity type, any other reoccurrence of the entity outside this range was ignored. Wherever no context was found or provided, every occurrence of the entities in the text was matched.

Finally, the entity index was matched in the context with the empty labels. The entity types with very little representations were removed but allowed for some imbalance to mimic real world cases as seen in table 2, by comparing the different numbers of occurrences of each entity. The entity type B-GROUP D, was the one least represented with only 167 entries.

The IOB format was also used, popularized by the CoNLL NER task [35] and initially proposed by Ramshaw & Marcus in 1995 [36]. In this format, "I" designates words inside an entity, "O" denotes non-entity words such as the punctuation, and "B" marks the beginning word of an entity [36]. This classification is used on table 2.

Entities	Abstract only	Abstract and methods	Abstract and methods (50 tokens)	Abstract and methods (512 tokens)
B-SUBJECTS	1853	3661	3661	3661
B-CONDITION	1384	1949	1949	1949
B-DESIGN	826	1393	1393	1393
B-GROUP A	3300	5498	5498	5498
B-GROUP B	2531	4730	4730	4730
B-GROUP C	562	1330	1330	1330
B-GROUP D	167	395	395	395
I-CONDITION	3689	5648	5648	5648
I-DESIGN	3176	5423	5423	5423

I-GROUP A	2098	3030	3030	3030
I-GROUP B	1553	2610	2610	2610
I-GROUP C	548	1303	1303	1303
I-GROUP D	230	348	348	348
I-SUBJECTS	1418	3681	3681	3681
O	538946	2416829	2416829	2416829

Table 2. Distribution of entity types in the 4 data sets.

2.3. Name Entity Recognition Training

For the training and finetuning process with V100 and T4 GPU, Google Colab has been used. The 4 data sets were split into training validation and test on the proportions of 80%, 10%, 10% respectively.

The performance of each model was assessed by comparing the mean F1-score. The ability of the model to learn evenly across all tags was looked at using the F1-score range (the difference between the maximum and minimum F1-score gotten for each tag).

BioElectra model was pretested and was posteriorly trained with the data sets and the learning rate which gave the best convergence F1-score, being these parameters presented in table 3.

Beside BioElectra were applied PubMedBert, BioLinkBert, and Clinical Longformer, which were trained using the best performing hyperparameters, being this information also presented in table 3.

Clinical Longformer is able to accept longer sequences of text, when compared with the other pre trained language models. For this reason, it was trained only with long texts, and hence applied to the data set composed by abstract and methods, as this data set is the only one where individual entry are consistently longer than 512 tokens. It was trained on a max token length of 4096, while the three other models used 512 tokens of maximum length and were applied to the other 3 data sets as well.

2.4. Hyperparameter Tuning

All the hyperparameter combinations used are presented in table 3, for the overall choice of hyperparameters the HuggingFace trainer arguments have been used. The epochs, learning rates and weight decay were varied. To evaluate the model in training and testing the F1-score for each entity type in the model has been computed. The model overall performance is determined by calculating the mean F1-score obtained.

BioElectra and PubMedBert have 108903183 training parameters, while BioLinkBert and Clinical Longformer have 107653647 and 148080399 respectively, these numbers were calculated recurring to the HuggingFace function.

To all training the adamw_torch optimizer has been applied. To preprocess the data sets into tokens the Fast tokenizer was applied. For all the experiments 15 tags have been used in each,

while punctuation marks of the data sets have been included as well.

Model	Applied Learning Rates	Weight Decay	Data set
BioElectra	$5 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-6}, 7.5 \times 10^{-4}, 5 \times 10^{-4}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract
	$5 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-6}, 7.5 \times 10^{-5}, 2.5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods
	$5 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-6}, 1 \times 10^{-7}, 1.25 \times 10^{-6}, 7.5 \times 10^{-7}, 2.5 \times 10^{-6}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods: 50 tokens
	$5 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-6}, 1 \times 10^{-4}, 2.5 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-4}, 3 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods: 512 tokens
	5×10^{-4}	4×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods: 512 tokens
BioLinkBert	$7.5 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-4}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract
	$7.5 \times 10^{-5}, 2.5 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods
	$5 \times 10^{-6}, 1 \times 10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods: 50 tokens
	$2.5 \times 10^{-5}, 3 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods: 512 tokens
PubMedBert	$7.5 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-4}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract
	$7.5 \times 10^{-5}, 2.5 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods
	$5 \times 10^{-6}, 1 \times 10^{-6}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods: 50 tokens
	$2.5 \times 10^{-5}, 3 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods: 512 tokens
Clinical Longformer	$8.5 \times 10^{-5}, 2.5 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-5}, 5 \times 10^{-4}, 1.25 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-5}$	3×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods
	5×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods
	5×10^{-5}	5×10^{-3}	Abstract and methods
	5×10^{-5}	5×10^{-4}	Abstract and methods

Table 3. Hyperparameters applied to the training of all 4 PLMs models.

3. RESULTS

The results of the mean F1-scores obtained are presented in table 4. Changing the leaning rates influenced the performance of the PLMs, as different models achieved optimal performance with different learning rates. While BioElectra demonstrated optimal performance with the

learning rate varying between 5×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-4} , for PubMedBert and BioLinkBert, the most effective learning rate was 5×10^{-5} , showcasing their robust performance between the range of 5×10^{-6} to 5×10^{-4} .

Clinical Longformer also exhibited its best performance at a learning rate of 5×10^{-5} ; however, its mean F1-score fell below that of PubMedBert, BioLinkBert, and BioElectra.

Among the data sets, the abstract and methods: 50 tokens, consistently produced great results across all models. The removal of punctuation marks from certain data sets did not significantly impact model output, for this reason, all models were evaluated with punctuation included.

PubMedBert achieved better results than the other models, with a mean F1-score of 0.64, closely followed by BioLinkBert at 0.6. Although the differences in results were marginal, the decisive metric was the range, representing the disparity between the maximum and minimum F1-scores for entity types. This range serves as a statistical measure of a model's ability to learn across both majority and minority entity types. PubMedBert achieved a range of 0.3, while BioLinkBert's range was markedly higher at 0.76.

PubMedBert achieved better results when applied to the minority tags, as shown in table 4, where PubMedBert successfully predicted entity type "Group D," while BioLinkBert produced blank predictions for the same category. This underlines PubMedBert's effectiveness in capturing nuances within the data, highlighting its potential for improved performance in handling minority entity types. These values of F1-scores, for the different entities, are in table 4.

Entities	Pretrained Language Models			
	BioElectra	BioLinkBert	PubMedBert	Clinical Longformer
B-CONDITION	0.55	0.65	0.59	0.35
I-CONDITION	0.64	0.63	0.59	0.44
B-DESIGN	0.62	0.65	0.63	0.53
I-DESIGN	0.73	0.76	0.74	0.59
B-SUBJECTS	0.59	0.67	0.55	0.33
I-SUBJECTS	0.53	0.60	0.50	0.38
B-GROUP A	0.72	0.69	0.75	0.46
I-GROUP A	0.60	0.55	0.57	0.48
B-GROUP B	0.67	0.56	0.69	0.36
I-GROUP B	0.48	0.53	0.50	0.23
B-GROUP C	0.64	0.61	0.72	0.00
I-GROUP C	0.53	0.36	0.60	0.00
B-GROUP D	0.71	0.00	0.81	0.00
I-GROUP D	0.38	0.00	0.71	0.00
Mean F1-score	0.60	0.60	0.64	0.35

Table 4. Best performing F1-score metrics and mean F1-score for all pretrained language models for each entity.

On figures 3, 4, 5 and 6 it is possible to see the mean F1-score for each PLM on each data set, where it was applied. BioElectra, BioLinkBert and PubMedBert have comparable results. PubMedBert and BioElectra are preferred over BioLinkBert as they learned and gave F1-scores for all entities, while BioLinkBert learned only the majority of entities and failed in the minority entities, which can be seen as an overall worse performance in these figures and is marked as null or lower values on table 4 results.

Figure 3. Mean F1-score for BioElectra performance with different data sets.

Figure 4. Mean F1-score for BioLinkBert performance with different data sets.

Figure 5. Mean F1-score for PubMedBert performance with different data sets.

Figure 6. F1-score of the Clinical Longformer, which was trained on the abstract and methods data set.

4. DISCUSSION

This study examined two 4 different Pretrained Language models for clinical entity recognition: pretrained language models (PLMs)—BioElectra, PubMedBert, BioLinkBert, and Clinical Longformer—for named entity recognition (NER) in clinical texts. The clinical tests were extracted in different types of text lengths and clinical entities. From these 4 models tested PubMedBert achieved superior results being able to classify entities in minority data, in which the other models struggled. In real-world scenarios, data imbalances are common, PubMedBert demonstrated its ability to perform well (mean F1-score between 0.60 and 0.81) even when the other models Clinical Longformer and BioLinkBert obtained a F1-score of zero. This disparity is crucial, as it highlights PubMedBert's superior capacity to learn minority tags. The model's performance on skewed data, specifically its ability to produce results for minority tags was demonstrated even without utilizing data balancing techniques.

A surprising outcome was the Clinical Longformer's approximately 50 percent lower mean F1-score compared to other models, despite its capability to process longer text sequences. A different approach was chosen for this model when compared with the other three used models, and this limits the extrapolation of the results. From the literature, it is suggested that the increased length of text would lead to better learning of the models [6], our results contradicted this assumption, and more work needs to be done in uncovering the reasons for these unexpected results. This is not the only surprising result, the data set of abstract and methods with segments of just 50 words, outperformed data sets with longer texts and closely matched the abstract with methods data set, on all models training.

The F1-scores obtained in this work are lower when compared with some other literature studies, but this can be explained by the nature of the data sets as the included data highly influence the results obtained. These results show the importance of the data set format, quality, and labelling processes. Most of the Named Entity Recognition works rely on publicly available data sets that have been refined and labelled to suit the task, resulting in high F1-scores [37], [38]. However, for applications with complex, and interrelated entity types, fitted data sets become necessary. The data set of Tut-All uses intermediary steps of validation, is more segmented than the publicly available, as it has extra preprocessing steps done by internal peer review, refining the data sets publicly available can be more realistic when compared with the public data sets. Hence the results achieved in this research, are most probably more useful for this type of analysis, but also more moderated in results, highlighting the need for further developments to be built upon this work.

Future works can focus on better fine tuning and standardization to achieve better results. The possibility of improving results by segmenting the data set with a focus on using complete sentences for better learning is also considered. To address overfitting and enhance model generalization, increasing the number of data sets is essential.

Finetuning the Clinical Longformer could benefit from warm-up steps [39], potentially improving performance and enabling evaluation of clinical text with extended token lengths. Varying epochs during training helped alleviate overfitting, but this remained a persistent issue.

The adjustment of learning rates and weight decay was crucial for achieving optimal convergence.

Gu et. al has shown that the tagging methodology and dummification could have different results in PubMedBert, future works could explore creating other fitted data sets with other methods [40]. In this research, the data set was chunked by linearly counting a set number of tokens, this can be improved by chunking with full stops or other sentence terminating punctuations. This will ensure the chunks of text from which the models are learning from are complete sentences or phrases. Also, augmentation techniques could be used to improve the data set or more records could be explored using the SWT to increase the data set for future works.

The use of the entities could also be further explored, as the current methods are to label it once, but ignore it in every other occurrence. However, this could potentially confuse the model if they are used in different contexts.

For real clinical application, the trustworthiness of the results is an important factor that could determine if fine-tuned PLMs can be used in the field, without human supervision in the subsequent steps.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Biomedical PLMs can be very useful for automated analysis of clinical entities in scientific texts.

- To fully utilize the biomedical pretrained language models in clinical applications, the performance through refining the data set is necessary.
- Future annotations with more data have the potential to improve the model.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Collobert, J. Weston, J. Com, M. Karlen, K. Kavukcuoglu, and P. Kuksa, "Natural Language Processing (Almost) from Scratch," 2011.
- [2] S. Raza, D. J. Reji, F. Shajan, and S. R. Bashir, "Large-scale application of named entity recognition to biomedicine and epidemiology," *PLOS Digital Health*, vol. 1, no. 12, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1371/journal.pdig.0000152.
- [3] Y. J. Park, G. J. Yang, C. B. Sohn, and S. J. Park, "GPDminer: a tool for extracting named entities and analyzing relations in biological literature," *BMC Bioinformatics*, vol. 25, no. 1, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1186/s12859-024-05710-z.
- [4] D. L. Sackett, W. M. C. Rosenberg, J. A. M. Gray, R. B. Haynes, and W. S. Richardson, "Evidence based medicine: what it is and what it isn't," *BMJ*, vol. 312, no. 7023, pp. 71–72, Jan. 1996, doi: 10.1136/bmj.312.7023.71.
- [5] X. Liu *et al.*, "Reporting guidelines for clinical trial reports for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the CONSORT-AI extension," *Nat Med*, vol. 26, no. 9, pp. 1364–1374, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41591-020-1034-x.

- [6] L. Ismail, H. Materwala, A. P. Karduck, and A. Adem, "Requirements of Health Data Management Systems for Biomedical Care and Research: Scoping Review," *J Med Internet Res*, vol. 22, no. 7, p. e17508, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.2196/17508.
- [7] S. Liu, A. Wang, X. Xiu, M. Zhong, and S. Wu, "Evaluating Medical Entity Recognition in Health Care: Entity Model Quantitative Study," *JMIR Med Inform*, vol. 12, p. e59782, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.2196/59782.
- [8] C. Chakraborty, M. Bhattacharya, S. Pal, and S. S. Lee, "From machine learning to deep learning: Advances of the recent data-driven paradigm shift in medicine and healthcare," Jan. 01, 2024, *Elsevier B.V.* doi: 10.1016/j.crbiot.2023.100164.
- [9] L. Hong, M. Luo, R. Wang, P. Lu, W. Lu, and L. Lu, "Big Data in Health Care: Applications and Challenges," *Data Inf Manag*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 175–197, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.2478/dim-2018-0014.
- [10] J. B. D. . Joshi, *Proceedings, 2016 IEEE International Conference on Big Data : Dec 05-Dec 08, 2015, Washington D.C., USA.* IEEE, 2016.
- [11] P. Fernainy, A. A. Cohen, E. Murray, E. Losina, F. Lamontagne, and N. Sourial, "Rethinking the pros and cons of randomized controlled trials and observational studies in the era of big data and advanced methods: a panel discussion," *BMC Proc*, vol. 18, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1186/s12919-023-00285-8.
- [12] M. G. Titler, "Section II: Evidence-Based Practice Chapter 7. The Evidence for Evidence-Based Practice Implementation."
- [13] P. B. Burns, R. J. Rohrich, and K. C. Chung, "The levels of evidence and their role in evidence-based medicine," *Plast Reconstr Surg*, vol. 128, no. 1, pp. 305–310, Jul. 2011, doi: 10.1097/PRS.0b013e318219c171.
- [14] E. Hariton and J. J. Locascio, "Randomised controlled trials – the gold standard for effectiveness research: Study design: randomised controlled trials," Dec. 01, 2018, *Blackwell Publishing Ltd.* doi: 10.1111/1471-0528.15199.
- [15] F. Liu and P. Demosthenes, "Real-world data: a brief review of the methods, applications, challenges and opportunities," Dec. 01, 2022, *BioMed Central Ltd.* doi: 10.1186/s12874-022-01768-6.
- [16] K. Yoshida *et al.*, "Use of Data from Multiple Registries in Studying Biologic Discontinuation: Challenges and Opportunities HHS Public Access," 2013.
- [17] J. Li *et al.*, "A comparative study of pre-trained language models for named entity recognition in clinical trial eligibility criteria from multiple corpora," *BMC Med Inform Decis Mak*, vol. 22, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1186/s12911-022-01967-7.
- [18] H. Chopra *et al.*, "Revolutionizing clinical trials: the role of AI in accelerating medical breakthroughs," *Int J Surg*, vol. 109, no. 12, pp. 4211–4220, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1097/JS9.0000000000000705.
- [19] H. Chopra *et al.*, "Revolutionizing clinical trials: the role of AI in accelerating medical breakthroughs," *Int J Surg*, vol. 109, no. 12, pp. 4211–4220, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1097/JS9.0000000000000705.
- [20] D. S. Asudani, N. K. Nagwani, and P. Singh, "Impact of word embedding models on text analytics in deep learning environment: a review," *Artif Intell Rev*, vol. 56, no. 9, pp. 10345–10425, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10462-023-10419-1.

- [21] J. Pennington, R. Socher, and C. Manning, “Glove: Global Vectors for Word Representation,” in *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, Stroudsburg, PA, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2014, pp. 1532–1543. doi: 10.3115/v1/D14-1162.
- [22] A. Vaswani *et al.*, “Attention Is All You Need.”
- [23] M. E. Peters *et al.*, “Deep contextualized word representations,” Feb. 2018, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1802.05365>
- [24] J. Howard and S. Ruder, “Universal Language Model Fine-tuning for Text Classification,” Jan. 2018, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1801.06146>
- [25] Supriyono, A. P. Wibawa, Suyono, and F. Kurniawan, “Advancements in natural language processing: Implications, challenges, and future directions,” *Telematics and Informatics Reports*, vol. 16, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.teler.2024.100173.
- [26] M. Košprdić, N. Prodanović, A. Ljajić, B. Bašaragin, and N. Milošević, “From Zero to Hero: Harnessing Transformers for Biomedical Named Entity Recognition in Zero- and Few-shot Contexts,” May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.artmed.2024.102970.
- [27] K. R. Kanakarajan, B. Kundumani, and M. Sankarasubbu, “BioELECTRA:Pretrained Biomedical text Encoder using Discriminators,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/>
- [28] R. Tinn *et al.*, “Fine-tuning large neural language models for biomedical natural language processing,” *Patterns*, vol. 4, no. 4, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.patter.2023.100729.
- [29] Y. Gu *et al.*, “Domain-Specific Language Model Pretraining for Biomedical Natural Language Processing,” *ACM Trans Comput Healthc*, vol. 3, no. 1, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1145/3458754.
- [30] L. Fang, Q. Chen, C.-H. Wei, Z. Lu, and K. Wang, “Bioformer: an efficient transformer language model for biomedical text mining.” [Online]. Available: https://huggingface.co/emilyalsentzer/Bio_ClinicalBERT
- [31] M. Yasunaga, J. Leskovec, and P. Liang, “LinkBERT: Pretraining Language Models with Document Links,” Mar. 2022, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2203.15827>
- [32] Y. Li, R. M. Wehbe, F. S. Ahmad, H. Wang, and Y. Luo, “A comparative study of pretrained language models for long clinical text,” *J Am Med Inform Assoc*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 340–347, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1093/jamia/ocac225.
- [33] Y. Li, R. M. Wehbe, F. S. Ahmad, H. Wang, and Y. Luo, “Clinical-Longformer and Clinical-BigBird: Transformers for long clinical sequences,” Jan. 2022, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2201.11838>
- [34] K. R. Kanakarajan, B. Kundumani, and M. Sankarasubbu, “BioELECTRA:Pretrained Biomedical text Encoder using Discriminators,” 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/>
- [35] E. F. Tjong, K. Sang, and F. De Meulder, “Introduction to the CoNLL-2003 Shared Task: Language-Independent Named Entity Recognition.” [Online]. Available: <http://lcg-www.uia.ac.be/conll2003/ner/>
- [36] L. A. Ramshaw and M. P. Marcus, “Text Chunking using Transformation-Based Learning.”
- [37] K. Xue, Y. Zhou, Z. Ma, T. Ruan, H. Zhang, and P. He, “Fine-tuning BERT for Joint Entity and Relation Extraction in Chinese Medical Text,” Aug. 2019, [Online]. Available:

<http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.07721>

- [38] A. Jolly, V. Pandey, I. Singh, and N. Sharma, “Exploring Biomedical Named Entity Recognition via SciSpaCy and BioBERT Models,” *Open Biomed Eng J*, vol. 18, no. 1, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.2174/0118741207289680240510045617.
- [39] I. Beltagy, M. E. Peters, and A. Cohan, “Longformer: The Long-Document Transformer,” Apr. 2020, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2004.05150>
- [40] Y. Gu *et al.*, “Domain-Specific Language Model Pretraining for Biomedical Natural Language Processing,” *ACM Trans Comput Healthc*, vol. 3, no. 1, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1145/3458754.